

CASE STUDY ON THE INFLUENCE OF COVID 19 ON THE MANAGEMENT OF STRUCTURAL AND INVESTMENT FUNDS

Author(s)*: Anastasia CORCIU ¹, Liviu Onoriu MARIAN ², Hajnalka-Andrea SZŐKE ³,
Carmen Magdalena MOTEA ⁴, Cristina Andra CHILUT ⁵
Positions: PhD Student ¹, Prof. PhD², PhD Student³ PhD Student⁴, PhD Student⁵
University: Technical University of Cluj-Napoca
Address: Cluj-Napoca, Memorandumului Str., No. 28, Romania
Email: ncorciu@mail.ru¹, liviu.marian@yahoo.com ², szoke.andrea14@gmail.com³,
carmen_motea@yahoo.com.uk⁴, andrachilut@yahoo.com⁵
Webpage: <http://www.utcluj.ro/>

Abstract

Purpose - to analyze the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the management process of European projects.

Methodology/approach - bibliographic study method - due to the multitude of information that is constantly exploding, this method is vital to any research study. Observation. Statistical data analysis. The case study method - is a suitable method if a full and in-depth investigation of a topic is desired.

Findings - Improving the management process of European projects. Establishing action strategies in case of a new pandemic.

Research limitations/implications - research limitations are due to the fact that this research was conducted on a limited number of projects.

Practical implications - determining the factors that made it difficult or even suspended the process of carrying out project activities. Implementation of measures through which managers can improve the management process of European projects.

Originality/value - the originality of the paper will be confirmed through the observations, analyzes, case study and conclusions presented in this paper.

Key words: Project management, Structural and Investment Funds, pandemic.

Introduction

As in the case of the other areas, the pandemic caused by the Sars-Cov2 virus has been a real problem both in terms of Structural and Investment Funds, but also in the case of the management process and efficiency of the projects financed by them. The negative effects of the pandemic have emerged since the first months of 2020, manifesting in various ways, such as the inability of employees to carry out the activities of the projects established by the funding applications and funding contracts, and up to the loss of human resources employed in within the projects, but also of the people enrolled in the target group, as a result of the large number of victims produced by the new virus.

In the fight with all these problems, but also with many others, which presented, at that time, an equally high level of gravity, the project managers put the greatest effort. They were in a continuous search for the best solutions in order to mitigate or even avoid the negative effects of the pandemic on the managed projects, but also to resume, as quickly and safely as possible, the activities of the projects and their successful implementation. Each solution found, as well as every decision taken in order to successfully carry out project activities during this period, came, however, with a huge baggage of new responsibilities that the managers had to assume and learn to manage overnight. Certainly, this period was decisive in the process of distinguishing the best managers, because this was precisely the period when each leader demonstrated how well he knows how to manage crisis situations, how effectively he knows how to react in stressful situations, but most importantly, how well he knew how to predict the threats that may arise in the project implementation process and what kind of solutions can be applied, regardless of whether we are talking about the human resources department, technical department or financial department of the project.

Specific aspects of european projects during the COVID 19 pandemic reflected in specialized literature

The Structural and Investment Funds represent one of the main instruments through which the European Union intervenes in the internal politics of the member states and not only. Namely, this is the instrument through which it is aimed, not so much to influence public decisions, but to direct them towards the recovery of the least developed sectors of the states.

Through these so-called invisible weapons:

- ✓ "The European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) - aims to strengthen economic and social cohesion at the regional level by investing in sectors that enhance growth, with a view to generating a higher degree of competitiveness and job creation. At the same time, the ERDF finances cross-border cooperation projects
 - ✓ Cohesion Fund (CF) - invests in people, focusing on improving opportunities in employment and education. It also aims to support disadvantaged people who face the risk of poverty or social exclusion
 - ✓ European Social Fund (ESF) - invests in green growth and sustainable development and improves interconnection in Member States with a GDP below 90%"(The European Commission, 2014)
 - ✓ "European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) - focuses on solving specific problems faced by rural areas in the EU"(The European Commission, 2015)
 - ✓ European Maritime and Fisheries Fund (FEPAM) – encourages fishermen to adopt sustainable practices and helps communities in coastal areas to diversify their activities for a better livelihood
- wich make up the Structural and Investment Funds, the European Union leads a continuous struggle to promote principles such as social inclusion, environmental protection, non-discrimination, positive competitiveness in business or equal opportunities.

The European Union intervention action through the Structural and Investment Funds is materialized, in the initial phase, by the establishment of intervention programs at the beginning of each financing period, and in the final phase by providing the necessary investments for the implementation of projects whose activities and objectives aim to contribute to the achievement of european objectives. In this context, in my opinion, the projects can be likened to the cells of the human body, which, although they are, mostly, microscopic and innumerable, the death of each one affects the proper functioning of the human body. This also happens when one or more projects, for some reason, are not successfully implemented, thus a stagnation in the development process of the targeted area is observed.

In the pandemic years, this aspect was all the more highlighted, because, precisely during this period, most of the previously started projects encountered a lot of obstacles that made it difficult or even impossible to continue the implementation of the projects. Thus, some projects have not managed to overcome all the difficulties yet, even at the present time, others, however, have ended up being a great success. In this case, the responsibility, both for the failures and for the successes of each individual project, is borne equally by the European community, and by the project managers themselves. This is because, while the European community and the member states do not currently have a guide of good practices that can be applied in the project management process in such periods in order to reduce the negative effects, the project managers, unfortunately, they revealed the lack of experience in making decisions in emergency situations, but also their level of stress resistance.

However, the pandemic has managed to highlight not only the managerial gaps of projects, but primarily the gaps in the entire management processes of today's societies.

Problems caused by the pandemic

Despite the numerous analyzes carried out at the time of drafting the projects' funding applications, the pandemic caused by COVID-19 was not foreseen in any of them. Dozens or maybe even hundreds of SWOT analyzes were done, but unfortunately, in the threat quadrant, non of the managers mentioned a possible pandemic that could turn all our work upside down and keep us locked up in our houses for such a long time. For this reason, just like all of us, project managers were caught by surprise when, overnight, they had to deal with a huge number of problems that started to confront the projects they were managing.

From my point of view, one of the biggest problems faced by the project managers during that period was the obligation to suspend the activities carried out. This problem in turn generated another problem, namely the fact that thousands of employees, including project managers, were left without income from the projects, a factor that further intensified the fear that citizens already had.

Another problem that the project managers faced was that during this time the virus claimed a lot of lives. This factor negatively influenced the projects from two points of view, because, on the one hand, the victims were the experts employed within the projects, and on the other hand, they were people enrolled in the target group.

The project managers who nevertheless managed not to suspend their activity during this period, but also the others, at the time of the resumption of activity, had to comply with several rules, such as:

- Respecting the maximum number of people present in the meetings;
- Ensuring a distance of at least 2 meters between participants;
- Equipping rooms with disinfectant;
- Wearing protective masks;
- Temperature check, etc.

Analyzing the above, we can easily realize that the most affected projects during the pandemic were those related to education. Here we are talking both about the projects that involved carrying out practical activities together with children 0-16 years old, in order to bring and maintain them in educational institutions, as well as the projects that involved training activities for adults.

Solutions for managers

There are several solutions that project managers would be able to accommodate them during the pandemic. The most important, however, in my opinion, is that of digitization. The pandemic managed to demonstrate once again the low level of digitization not only of the state public administration, but also of other public or private institutions. Appropriate endowment and digitization of institutions would allow:

- the continuation of project activities in the online environment;
- holding work sessions in the online environment;
- conducting training courses within the projects in the online environment, etc.

Despite the multiple benefits that technology currently provides, due to a lack of equipment, licenses, or even knowledge related to the manipulation of electronic devices, some managers did not manage, at the time of the installation of the state of emergency, to pass at least part of the project activities in the online environment, others, however, unfortunately, have not been able to do so until now. Thus, in the event of a new pandemic wave and the installation of a new state of emergency, some managers would be as caught by surprise as they were two years ago. Closely related to digitization is the adoption of the electronic signature. Thus, by means of digital signatures, it was possible to reduce the number of physical contacts between project employees, but also between them and other institutions.

Another solution that the project managers could have implemented in this period of crisis is to reduce the number of participants present in the activities. Although this requires a greater effort by managers and experts, and also greater expenses, nevertheless, it is a way that allows the resumption and carrying out of activities, which ultimately allows the successful implementation of the project.

Another solution was to ensure a sufficiently large space for project activities, so that the participants could respect the minimum distance of two meters. There would still be a lot of solutions that the managers of the projects financed from the Social and Investment Funds could have implemented during that period, especially since the European Union itself was not reluctant, intervening immediately by reallocating the funds in order to reduce the negative effects of the pandemic and the fastest possible resolution of the problems caused by it in the various areas of the member states and not only.

Despite the countless failures of European project management due to the pandemic, however, at the end of 2020, the results of the European Union's Structural and Investment Funds recorded up to the end of 2020 looked like this:

- "3 million enterprises supported in the process of continuing the activity;
- 236,500 new jobs created
- 45,000 people supported in the process of social inclusion, employment or participation in education;
- 2 million sustainable projects in the field of agriculture and rural development implemented;
- maintaining 31,500 jobs and creating 4,000 new jobs in the maritime and fishing sector"(The European Commission, 2021).

According to statistical data, in 2020, despite the pandemic situation, the level of expenses recorded within the projects increased. For example, in terms of cohesion policy "an acceleration in the level of project spending, reaching 39% of the planned allocation (€12 billion) by the end of 2020, up from 26% at the end of 2019..."(The European Commission, 2021). These statistical data demonstrate, however, that despite the difficult situation created by the pandemic at the beginning of 2020, by the end of the same year project managers managed to reorganize their activity and achieve even better results than the previous year.

Case study - Analysis of absorption level of European Structural and Investment Funds in the pandemic period

In general, regarding the level of absorption of Structural and Investment Funds recorded in the period 2014-2020, a period in which the pandemic also occurred, Italy is in the top of the countries, followed by Poland, then Spain, Romania being in seventh place(The European Commission, 2022). Thus, in 2020, Italy recorded an absorption of 44% of the money allocated by the European Union, meaning 19,860,371,450 EUR(The European Commission, 2022), Poland recorded an absorption of 59% of the money allocated by the European Union, meaning 50,510,591,580 EUR(The European Commission, 2022), Spain recorded an absorption of 45% of the money allocated by the European Union, meaning 17,918,461,720 EUR(The European Commission, 2022), and Romania recorded an absorption of 50% of the money allocated by the European Union, meaning 15,536,030,600 EUR(The European Commission, 2022). In 2021, the level of absorption recorded by the states increases, Romania reaching 57%, meaning 19,711,010,169 EUR(European Commission, 2022).

Conclusions

In conclusion, despite the attempts of the pandemic to turn an entire economy upside down, the European Union, together with the villages that enjoy projects financed from the Structural and Investment Funds, have once again proven that the power lies in the many and that a good organization can help us overcome any obstacle. From our point of view, even if, as we saw in the content of the paper, the individual entities, led by the project managers or even the states led by their leaders, were not at all prepared for such a disaster, the ability to reorganize and rethinking the strategies that most of these subjects showed afterwards helped us to avoid a lot of negative effects. We also believe that the best management and removal of unforeseen dangers was demonstrated by the leadership of the European Union, which managed in an extremely short period to reorganize itself from scratch and find in the shortest possible period the most good solutions to the problems that arise. A very good example is the very process of reallocating the Structural and Investment Funds and the creation of NextGenerationEU, which, according to the European Union, "is more than a recovery plan - it is a once-in-a-lifetime chance to emerge from the pandemic stronger, to transform our economies and societies and to rebuild Europe in a way that benefits us all" European Commission, 2022). Namely, this proved to us once again that we live in a strong community, with the ability to analyze and solve problems.

References

European Commission

2014

Introducere în politica de coeziune a UE 2014-2020

European Commission

2021

Summary report of the programme annual implementation reports covering implementation in 2014-2020

Stephany Griffith-Jones, Natalya Naqvi

2021

Industrial Policy and Risk Sharing in Public Development Banks: Lessons for the Post- COVID Response from the EIB and EFSI. Revista de Economia Mundial.

Matt Rees

2020

How to fight a crisis.

European Investment Bank, <https://www.eib.org/en/stories/efsi-legacy>

Press release

2021

Investment Funds: shifted priorities in the post-pandemic growth

https://www.ey.com/en_lu/news/2021/10/investment-funds--shifted-priorities-in-the-post-pandemic-growth

Vasilis Margaras

2022

Flexibility measures for European Structural and Investment Funds in response to the coronavirus outbreak

<https://www.europarl.europa.eu/legislative-train/theme-regional-development-regi/file-coronavirus-flexibility-measures-for-esif-in-response-to-the-covid-19-outbreak>